

The Effect of Workplace Bullying on Employees' Job Satisfaction

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Abstract: *The main motive of current study was to investigate the relationship between workplace bullying and job satisfaction in faculty members of public sector universities of Sindh (i.e., Shah Abdul Latif University, Khairpur and Sukkur institute of business administration). The cross-sectional design, a close ended Survey was conducted among 209 faculty members of both institutions. The finding of this study point out that the bullying dimensions i.e., work related bullying and person related bullying were significantly, negatively related to job satisfaction. Further, the results of the universities i.e., Sukkur institute of business Administration and Shah Abdul Latif University Khairpur, Sindh, were also compared. The employees of Sukkur institute of business administration perceived work related bullying more as compared to Shah Abdul Latif University while employees of Shah Abdul Latif University perceived person related bullying more as compared to Sukkur institute of business administration. The implications of the study are discussed.*

Key words: *Workplace Bullying (Work-Related Bullying and Person-Related Bullying) Job Satisfaction*

1.0 Introduction

Bullying is defined as “situations at work where someone’s behaviour is perceived to be systematically aimed at frustrating or tormenting an employee who is unable to defend him or herself, or escape from this situation” (Einarsen, et al. 2003, p.6). Workplace bullying is an adverse attitude and behavior that one faces in the organization as disparity in the power being the root cause to that and resultantly it creates tension and negativity in the environment (Einarsen 1996, Hoel, Cooper 2000 and Zapf, et al, 1996). Above researches have clearly identified that the reason for creating this bullying at work place is due to the perception that there is no parity in the power and power is utilized to influence and negatively impact the less powerful which ultimately develops an uneasy environment in the place of work. Taking above research into the consideration it becomes essential to investigate this workplace bullying. According to Vartia (1996), workplace, bullying is a widespread and interesting topic of research studies in several European countries as the first study on bullying was conducted in UK and term bullying is used in UK and Ireland in terms of intimidation. Workplace bullying institution (WBI) terms workplace bullying as a widespread

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area, which refers to hurting and abuse of individuals. It consists of verbal misuse, unfriendly nonverbal practices or officiously interfere with some body's accomplishing work power. In this condition mostly weaker people and employees become the victims and this victimization may be the cause of disturbance that organizations face in different span of times hurting their organizational output, in general and public sector universities in particular. One of the important attitudinal outcomes resulting from the employees' perception of workplace bullying is decrease in the job satisfaction level. The concept of job satisfaction is defined as "an outcome of supportive work related environment with favorable conditions physically and psychologically" (Hoppock, 1935, p.77). Many researchers have worked to observe the impacts of workplace bullying on job satisfaction of employees. O'driscoll et al (2011) have found in their research study that bullying makes people remain absent from job, stressful, lack of interest in job and job satisfaction. Quine (2001) has determined the significant results in community nurses in UK and indicated some important effects of workplace bullying as lower level of job satisfaction, higher level of anxiety and depression, and the supportive help at work to protect them from the different damaging effects of bullying. An other study conducted by Oghojfor et, al. (2012) shows that workplace bullying has bad effects on employees job satisfaction at the all organizational levels. Thomas, R. (2008) and Cooper-Thomas, et,al (2011) found out that health, travel ,hospitality and travel in New Zealand are the sectors in which work place bullying is higher than international standards. As suggested by Namine and Needham et al. (2003) and Rigby (2002) that few researchers have also observed about scarcity of research work in work place bullying and job satisfaction. According to them relationship between the workplace bullying and job satisfaction of employees is still unknown and researchable. Some researchers like Saunders et al. (2007) have described that Sweden was the country which took the first step to formulate the anti-bullying law and Canada became the first country to formally execute this anti bullying law with a view to stop this bullying and to curb the negative impacts created by it in organizations. Czaika and Begley (1993) in their research gave the opinion that employee who are highly attached with organization are less effected by outcomes of bullying like cognitive and physical trauma, lesser satisfaction in job and plans to leave the job in comparison to those who less attached with organization. Hoel et al (2003) and Quine (1999) believe that highly committed individuals are less effected by bullying outcomes like intentions to leave the job and remain absent from job. According to researcher Bullying has become a major occupational stressor that leads to a decreased in moral, health, performance, job satisfaction and other work-out comes, and increased absents, stress & turnover, (Cooper et, al, 1998), Due to above causes of bullying , results are stressful working environment which may impacts employees job satisfaction level. Therefore, this study has conducted in that perspective to determine the effects of workplace bullying on job satisfaction. As workplace bullying is a kind of harassment that is percieving as a very important management problem for employers and as well as for the organizations. Therefore, in this study, an effort has been made to determine the influence of workplace bullying on job

satisfaction of employees in education service sector specifically focusing on the faculty members of two higher education institutions i.e., Shah Abdul Latif Univeristy (SALU) and Sukkur Institute of Business Administration (SIBA) in sindh province of Pakistan. The effect of two dimension of workplace bullying ie., work related and person relaed bullyng has been tested on employees' job satisfaiton.

2.0. Literature Review

2.1 The outcomes of Workplace Bullying

Takaki et al, (2010) concluded the workplace bullying is a very important and significant cause of depression, according to their study evidences show that the people and employees who experience bullying at working environment they come out with various negative outcomes and psychological health issues and they are mostly under the depression and stress problems. Keashli and Neuman (2010) found that negative and adverse behaviors involved in work place bullying at academic staff results in creating barriers to stop an employee to achieve professional excellence and objectives. They further found that bullying is aimed to disturb professional accomplishment of an employee. Mckay, Huberman Arnold, Fratzl and Thomas (2008) conducted research on work place bullying in a university at Canada. According to them extreme cognitive disturbance, mental stress and trauma, helplessness, depression are the outcomes of bullying.

2.2. Workplace Bullying Among University Employees

The research studies on Bullying among university employees were mostly conducted by Scandinavian researchers, According to Keashly & Neuman (2010), few research studies in academia, regarding bullying, were conducted in United States, Canada, UK, and New Zealand. As summarized by Keashly and Neuman (2010), rates of experienced bullying in university level varied, from country to country. Keashly and Neuman (2010) research find out that bullying in academia were relatively higher. Further, It was also observed that different bullying measurements instruments were used to compare the rates of bullying in different countries prospects to get the findings regarding bullying in academia. Further, the two dimension of workplace bullying and job satisfaction is discussed;

2.3. Person Related Bullying

Person-related bullying consist of such behaviors as offensive comments, engaging in undue bantering, dispersal of gossips, roamers, hurting, continual denigration, playing practical jocks and engaging in intimidation (Beswick, Gore, and Palferman, et al. (2006) found that person related bullying adversely effects on employees' health and have capacity to create severe psychic disorders like anxiety, variations of mood, depression and more severe cognitive disorders.

2.4. Work Related Bullying

Work-related bullying consists of behaviors as to give unreasonable deadlines or unmanageable workloads, excessive monitoring of work or assigning meaningless

tasks and even no tasks. Einarsen and Raknes (1997) defined work place bullying as continuous intentional and unintentional actions by an employee causing tension, mental trauma to another employee at work Beswick, Gore and Palferman (2006) observed that work place bullying involves giving unrealistic deadlines, highly unachievable, insignificant, and vague information.

2.5. Job Satisfaction

Hoppock (1935) defined job satisfaction as an outcome of supportive work related environment with favorable conditions physically and psychologically. Vroom (1964) consider an employee satisfied from job if he is totally involved and committed with work and task he is assigned. Santhapparaj and Alam (2005) found that if an employee is satisfied with promotion policies, pay, and conditions of work and research support then he has higher chances to have higher job satisfaction. Noordin and Jusoff (2009) investigated two hundred and thirty seven academic staff members of Public Sector University in Malaysia. They reported moderate level of job satisfaction in them.

2.6. Relationship between Workplace Bullying and Job Satisfaction

Although, bullying phenomena is turned into subject matter for research studies since the mid-1990s but the relationship between workplace bullying and job satisfaction is unrecognized or less focused (Namie &, 2003; Rigby, 2002; Cooper and Marshal (1976), Naumann, et al. (1993), in research study on work place bullying found that work place bullying adversely effects employees and they become less satisfied with their job. Hauge, et al. (2010), Laymann (1996), Quine (1999) reported that workplace bullying is one of major factors which creates stress in the organization. Oghojafo, et al. (2012) conducted a study to find the effects of workplace bullying on job satisfaction. According to their suggestions workplace bullying at the organizational level negatively affects employee's job satisfaction and their job commitment. Hauge, et al (2010), Quine (1999) Leyman (1996) conducted a research to point out the conclusion of various studies regarding impact of workplace bullying on job satisfaction. According to their findings there are many studies in which workplace bullying has been perceived and accepted as a very important occupational stress factor. Therefore based on these studies, it can be concluded that work place bullying negatively affects job satisfaction.

Einarsen and Rakens (1997), describe different dimension of work place bullying i.e., work related and person related bullying. According to their research study work related bullying involve bullying caused by creation of hurdles in performing work or denying effected person from his job assignments partially or fully. Further, regarding the person related bullying, Einarsen and Hoel (1997) argues that person related bullying is caused due to adverse actions on personality like making and spreading negative perceptions for victim, making victim socially inactive and making them difficult to breath. Thus, overall, based on these findings we propose that;

2.7 Hypothesis

H. The dimensions of workplace bullying such as work-related bullying and person-related bullying are negatively related to job satisfaction among the faculty members of public sector universities (SALU and SIBA) in Sindh.

2.8 Research Model

Figure 1: Research Model of Workplace Bullying

3.0 Methodology

3.1 Data and Sample

Population for this study is 300 faculty members of public sector universities (SALU & IBA). All the male and female faculty members working in different departments of SALU & SIBA were sample of this study. 211 was sample size, which was determined by using the Saunders at el. (2009) sampling table. Convenient sampling technique was used to get data from faculty of SALU & SIBA. Data were collected by using primary data collection method. A Likert type of survey questionnaire was used to collect data.

3.2 Measures

The dimensions of Workplace bullying i.e., work related and person related bullying were measured using the 19 Items (NAQ) Negative Act Questionnaire developed by Einarsen and Raknes (1997). The job satisfaction was measured using the 05 items questionnaire developed by Brayfield (1951). In this study, data has been tested by using descriptive statistics, and regression analysis through statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) version 20.

3.3 Controls

Moreno- Jimenez et al. (2008) in their study find out that there is a difference of level of workplace bullying that different people of different age-groups and gender feel. Einarsen and Skogstad (1996) observed that employees with older age feel more workplace bullying than employees having younger age. Cohen (2004) found out that male and female feel different level of bullying. Literature explains that, women are significantly more likely to be bullied targets than men. In other words, more women witness bullying

behavior than men. According to Bjorkqvist et al. (1994) and Moreno-Jimenez et al. (2008) their research reported that females were bullied significantly more than male coworkers. According to Jawahar, Keashly and Neuman (2010), when the relationship between persons become longer and increase interaction among them than the chances of brutal or aggressive behavior also enhanced. Keashly and Neuman (2010) concluded that among the staff and faculty, there is long term-relationship the workers who were long time in their position would experience bullying by their coworkers more often. Therefore, based on these findings we have included age, gender and experience as control variables. The demographic information of the respondent is given in table 1.

Table No. 01: Demographic Analyses for Age, Experience, and Gender of the Respondents

Age			
SALU	22 to 23 years	20	12.8
	Above 23 Years	136	87.2
IBA Sukkur	22 to 23 years	6	10.9
	Above 23 Years	49	89.1
Experience			
SALU	5 Years	104	66.7
	10 years	26	16.7
IBA Sukkur	Above 10 Years	26	16.7
	5 Years	26	47.3
	10 years	19	34.5
	Above 10 Years	10	18.2
Gender			
SALU	Male	99	63.5
	Female	57	36.5
IBA Sukkur	Male	39	70.9
	Female	16	29.1

4.0 Data Analysis and Results

The results of descriptive analysis and correlations are given in table 2.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics and Correlation analyses:

Institution	Variables	Experience	Gender	Age	WRB	PRB	JS
SIBA	Experience	1	.26**	.12	-.81**	-.10**	-.90**
	Gender		1	.27**	-.85**	-.45**	.86**
	Age			1	-.14	-.88*	.49
	WRB				1	.86**	-.73
	PRB					1	-.71
	JS						1
SALU	Experience	1	-.28*	.17	-.63**	-.67**	-.60**
	Gender		1	-.29*	-.25**	.34**	-.64**
	Age			1	.85	-.19	.49
	WRB				1	.64**	-.33**
	PRB					1	-.70**
	JS						1

**Correlations are significant at the 0.01 level.
* Correlations are significant at the 0.05 level.

The reliability of the variables is given in table 3.

Table No. 03: Reliability of Study Variables

Item name	Reliability scores
Work-related bullying	.70
Person-related bullying	.83
Job satisfaction	.89

In H2, we proposed that proposed that the relationship between dimensions of workplace bullying (work-related bullying and person-related bullying) and job satisfaction among faculty members of public sector universities (IBA & SALU) is significantly negative. The regression results showed that work-related bullying ($\beta = -.59$, $p < .01$) and person-related bullying ($\beta = -.40$, $p < .01$) has negative relationship at a significant level with job satisfaction, among the faculty members of IBA Sukkur. Further, in the case of SALU Khairpur, the results showed that work-related bullying ($\beta = -.46$, $p < .01$) and person-related bullying ($\beta = -.43$, $p < .01$) are negatively related to job satisfaction. Therefore H2 was fully supported. The results are given in table no. 4.

Table 4: Regression Analysis

Institution	Variables	R	B	Significance
SIBA	WRB	.83	-.59	0.03
	PRB		-.40	0.00
	WRB	.80	-.46	.000
	PRB		-.43	.000

Dependent Variable: Job Satisfaction

5.0 Discussion

The results described that the level of job satisfaction among the faculty members is negatively affected if they feel (hurdles in their work, excessive and unmanageable workload, unreasonable deadline of work) work-related bullying, and feel (insulting behaviors, excessive teasing and feel severe psychic disorders like anxiety, variation of mood, and possess sense of depersonalization) person-related bullying. In the perspective of comparison in both public sector universities i.e., SALU and SIBA, in the faculty of SIBA the effect of work-related bullying was more as compared to person related bullying on job satisfaction level of employees and similar was the case at SALU. Further, if we compare across the both organizations, the effect of work related bullying was more at SIBA as compared to SALU, on job satisfaction level while the effect of person related bullying was more at SALU as compared to SIBA. Overall, the results showed the significant negative effect of both the dimension of workplace bullying on job satisfaction of employees in both the organizations. These results are also consistent with the studies testing the effect of workplace bullying on job satisfaction. Such as Oghojafo, et al. (2012) found same results, as per their suggestions workplace bullying at the organizational level negatively affects employees job satisfaction and their job commitment. Hauge et al. (2010), Quine (1999), Leyman (1996) results showed an adverse impact of workplace bullying on job satisfaction.

6.0 Managerial Implications

This study is conducted in the public sector universities perspective for understanding the relationship of work behavior e.g. workplace bullying and work outcomes e.g. satisfaction of job. Current research study is incredibly significant as it put down some essential implications for universities, higher education commission and managements of universities, faculties and government. The management of the universities has to define the clear lines of communication for maintaining level of job satisfaction among the faculty and take efforts and some important steps to decrease and control over the effects of workplace bullying among employees, because workplace bullying which is an important creator of physical trauma, mental disorders, and lesser satisfaction of jobs among employees. Similarly, higher education commission should carefully take some actions and make policies for control of workplace bullying and make favorable environment for jobs in education system. The government should create anti-

bullying laws. This study also gives awareness about workplace bullying to faculty members of public sector universities.

7.0 Limitations and Future Directions

Further, to understand the effects of workplace bullying in higher education environment, study on institutional type and institutional environment would be helpful for us. This study is only limited to find the impacts of workplace bullying on job satisfaction among faculty of two public sector universities (SALU and SIBA) but future researchers may take it to locate the impacts and relationship of workplace bullying and job satisfaction among the faculties of all universities of Sindh or Pakistan level to obtain further and new widespread results.

The study timing may also have affected its results due to short time, and slighter resources of finance only two universities have been selected in the sample of current study.

Further due to lesser time we have find out the one aspect of study, that was the relationship of workplace bullying and job satisfaction, but there are many aspects need to find out them, like reasons and causes of workplace bullying, types of workplace bullying among faculties universities.

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